

D6.1 Report on initial use cases deployment and dispatcher prototype

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Abstract

This document follows the delivery of the project Proof of Concept release, describing the prototype architecture of Dispatcher, which implements the EOSC Data Player interface. Details including user authentication, plugin interface to support multiple target Virtual Research Environments as well as their specific implementations are discussed. The document is concluded with the experience with deployment of the initial use cases, the integrated Proof of Concept workflow in particular.

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Executive Summary

This document captures the development status of the *Dispatcher*, the key component of the *EOSC Data Player* service, at the time of the important project milestone “M3.2 Proof of concept (PoC) release”. Experience with its deployment, integration with specific use cases, and the workflow example of the PoC release are described as well.

The Dispatcher is a standalone service which accepts the *Package for Processing Datasets*, an RO-Crate object containing references of a workflow/tool to be executed and its input dataset(s). The Dispatcher translates the package into calls to various target environments, where the data and the workflows are prepared to be executed by the user.

Access to the service is authenticated via OpenID Connect (OIDC), and the architecture imposes strict use of end-user credentials only, which are delegated to the target services when necessary; no service identities are used to avoid complicated maintenance of authorization information.

The internal architecture of the Dispatcher is modular. The support for specific target environments is implemented in Python classes inherited from a common base. Both existing well-known target services and services spawned on demand via Infrastructure Manager (IM) and Kubernetes are supported.

Data files in the input packages are referenced, not copied. OneData can be used as a transport mechanism to deliver large data sets from repositories to the target environments.

The PoC release fully supports deployment in Galaxy and Jupyter/Binder. There is experimental support for ScienceMesh and Cryo-EM SPA (also known as Scipion), Haddock and MD Dashboard are in development. Support for further project use cases will be added gradually.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and scope of the document

The architecture of the technical solution of EOSC Data Commons, as described in **D3.1 EOSC Data Commons architecture, functional specifications no.1**, consists of two major components: the Matchmaker responsible for gathering information on available datasets, tools, and workflows and assembling those together according to the user's requirements, the and Data Player responsible for preparing the target environment where the user can apply the workflow/tool on the input datasets.

This deliverable captures the status of the Dispatcher and its connection to target environments at the time of early prototype, fulfilling the first project technical milestone "M3.2 Proof of concept release". It also summarizes the experience gathered in the first months of the project and outlines further development directions.

1.2. Structure of the document

Section 2 describes the architecture of the Dispatcher from a top-down perspective, starting with an overview, describing the principles of user authentication, data handling, and interactions with target environments. Finally it dives into more technical details.

Section 3 is dedicated to specific target environments with the details and specificities of the integration. Maturity of the integration varies in this prototype, some of the environments are fully integrated, others in development, and more advanced features are under consideration.

Section 4 goes back to the experience with the proof of concept integration (M3.2 Proof of concept (PoC) release). The solution is described in detail, discussing the current limitations.

2. Dispatcher architecture

2.1. Overview

The **Dispatcher** implements the input interface of the *EOSC Data Player* service provided by the project. On input, it consumes the *Package for Processing Datasets* – an RO-Crate object (either ZIP file or just its ro-crate-metadata.json) containing references to a workflow or another computational payload (e.g. code, call to another service API) and its input files. Its role in the architecture is in preparing the actual environment with the workflow and dataset, as discovered by *Matchmaker* and resolved by *Packager*. Interaction of these components is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 – Interaction of EOSC Data Commons components (from project proposal)

The target environments where the payload gets executed can be either existing ones (e.g. usegalaxy.eu or notebooks.egi.eu) or they can be created on demand via **Infrastructure Manager** or **Kubernetes**.

The Dispatcher is expected to operate in two modes:

- **Interactive:** The target environment for the workflow execution is set up, either using an existing service or spawning a dedicated one; input data are made available there (uploaded or referenced), and a link to the environment is passed back to the user who is expected to start the exploratory analysis on his/her own.
- **Batch:** The execution of the workflow in the target environment is triggered by the Dispatcher, the user is presented with final results (this mode is requested by the use cases and it will be implemented in the upcoming period; details are still to be clarified).

2.2. Request specification and life cycle

The Dispatcher input follows the [Research Object Crate \(RO-Crate\)](#) specification . It is either a single *ro-crate-metadata.json* file or a ZIP file containing *ro-crate-metadata.json* and additional data files. Here we provide a simplified example of [Galaxy workflow](#):

```
JSON
{
  "@context": [
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context",
    { "runsOn": "https://w3id.org/ro/terms/test#runsOn" }
  ],
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "name": "Galaxy Example Workflow",
      "description": "This is an example of a workflow using
the Galaxy platform.",
      "mainEntity" : { "@id": "#workflow" },
      "runsOn" : { "@id": "#destination" },
      "hasPart": [ { "@id": "#workflow" }, { "@id": "#textfile"
}, { "@id": "#destination" } ]
    },
    ...
    {
      "@id": "#workflow",
      "@type": ["File", "SoftwareSourceCode",
"ComputationalWorkflow"],
      "name": "Example galaxy workflow",
      ...
      "url":
"https://dockstore.org/.../Galaxy-Workflow-reverse_file_galaxy_workflow
.ga"
    },
    ...
    {
      "@id": "#textfile",
      "@type": "File",
      ...
    },
    {
      "@id": "#destination",
      "@type" : "Service",

```

```
    "url": "https://usegalaxy.eu/"  
  }  
]  
}
```

Figure 2 - Simplified RO-Crate of a Galaxy workflow

The json file encodes a graph of entities, with mandatory entries like *mainEntity* which refers to the workflow to be run, and *runsOn* which specifies the target environment.

The *mainEntity* must provide a *programmingLanguage* attribute referring to another entity of *ComputerLanguage* type, which specifies the workflow engine to use (Galaxy, Jupyter, ...). Miscellaneous small input files can be included in the ZIP archive and referred to from the json. Otherwise, inputs are referenced; either as a publicly accessible URL, or using specific data transport engines (currently only **OneData** is supported).

The destination (*runsOn* entity) refers to an existing service accessible by the user (e.g. **usegalaxy.eu**, **notebooks.egi.eu**). Alternatively, it can specify *serviceType* attribute **InfrastructureManager**, which triggers spawning a dedicated instance of the target environment via the Infrastructure Manager service .

In the current development version, the RO-Crate profile expected by Dispatcher is evolving rapidly and it is not specified formally yet. Instead, reference examples (all working) are provided in the **Dispatcher repository**.

On submission, the request is parsed and checked for correctness. When successful, it is assigned a unique identifier (uuid), and it is pushed into an internal queue, which reports major (self-explanatory) states: *pending*, *starting*, *retry*, *failure*, *success*, which are returned when Dispatcher is queried for the status (using the request uuid). Additional details could eventually be added to the status request.

The final *success* state means the request was successfully passed to the target Virtual Research Environment. In this case a redirection URL is returned to the end user or requesting service.

2.3. User authentication

The Dispatcher is designed as a service Application Programming Interface (API) to be called by other services or web user interface, and it does not provide an interface to be used directly by end users. User authentication/ authorisation is done by the means of **OAuth2** in cooperation with other EOSC Data Commons services (User Interface (UI) of Matchmaker in particular) and EGI Check-in, where the Dispatcher must be registered as a service. The expected Authentication and Authorization flow is outlined in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3 – Authentication and authorization flow of user interaction with UI, Dispatcher, and the target Virtual Research Environment (VRE)

The user starts interacting with the UI. At some point, authentication is requested by redirecting the user to the EGI Check-in login page. After the OAuth handshake is completed, the user is redirected back to the UI callback, and session cookies are created, which also contain the token to be used for further authorization to call the Dispatcher API to submit the request in the form of RO-Crate, which the UI prepares (with help of other services based on the Packager). The Dispatcher accepts the request by checking the token expected in *Authorization: HTTP* header. In turn, the token is used (after eventual token exchange) to talk to the target VRE (e.g. Galaxy, Jupyter) on behalf of the user. This is a key design principle, **no service identity** is used by the Dispatcher to talk to VREs. Finally, the Dispatcher assembles a redirect URL pointing to the prepared VRE; this URL may contain further authorization information (like the `?token=...` argument used by Jupyter).

For development purposes, the Dispatcher exposes an additional `/oauth2` path that redirects to EGI Check-in and then back with a token, which enables convenient access to testing API interface at `/docs`. Calling `/` also redirects to the auth sequence for convenience.

2.4. Data handling

The Data Player is designed to handle numerous independent data sources, including repositories in different organizations, and distributed data ecosystems based on Onedata. One of the main design goal is to use references to the data in its original location instead of passing their copies among the services, and to postpone copying as late as possible (that is, copy the file directly from its original location to the computing node where it is processed).

This approach brings the following benefits:

- increasing the reusability of datasets,
- minimizing the costs of data transfers and the required storage buffers for copies, and
- easier and more transparent provenance tracking.

The information about datasets for analysis is expressed in the Request Package (also known as Package for Processing Datasets). While it's technically possible, the data is never stored inside the Request Package; instead, the Package contains references to datasets. The Dispatcher serves as a bridge that passes data references built by the Matchmaker to execution environments, possibly translating the Request Package to a compatible format, but does not interact with the data.

The baseline method for expressing references reuses the RO-Crate's standard approach with HTTP URLs:

```
JSON
{
  "@id": "#textfile",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "simpletext_input",
  "url": "https://example-files.online-convert.com/document/txt/example.txt",
  "encodingFormat": "text/txt"
}
```

Figure 4 – Example of a reference to a file with HTTP URL in RO-Crate

This straightforward solution offers easy interoperability between data sources and execution services, most of which are compatible with the HTTP protocol. It's sufficient for open and public datasets and standardized repositories, but does not cover all scenarios addressed by EOSC DataCommons:

- support for different data storage technologies and data access protocols,
- support for non-public datasets (user-owned or sensitive data) available behind various authorization schemes.¹

¹ In many such cases, the data could be made accessible with a URL; however, such URL itself becomes sensitive information which should not be circulated via the RO-Crate. Therefore we discourage this scenario.

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To account for that, RO-Crate extensions and profiles are used. They augment the information carried by the Request Package, but do not modify (retain) the basic information, which is the baseline for interoperability. Below is an example of how the extensions are used to accommodate Onedata-specific information:

```
JSON
{
  "@id": "#image-to-process",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "Input Image",
  "url":
  "https://demo.onedata.org/api/v3/onezone/shares/data/0000000007E05967368617265
  4775696423396461.../content",
  "encodingFormat": "image/tiff",
  "onedata:onezoneDomain": "demo.onedata.org",
  "onedata:spaceId": "6e6b22d6f32b63db34fcfac53e52e233chd8ba",
  "onedata:fileId": "0000000007E059673686172654775696423396461",
  "onedata:publicAccess": true
}
```

Figure 5 – Example of a reference to a file with Onedata-specific identifiers

Clients and execution environments that are compatible with Onedata may use the information to access the data using Onedata-specific interfaces, some of which allow high-performance data processing (**Oneclient** - the POSIX native mount and OnedataFS - the PyFilesystem 2.0 plugin). On the other hand, non-aware recipients of the Request Package will ignore the extension, but may not be able to access the data (unless it's public and the url fallback is viable). To mitigate this and maximize data processing performance, the EOSC Data Commons project will strive to implement adequate data access logic in different execution environments to cover various data sources – since, beyond Onedata, other technologies will be onboarded. Some use cases in EOSC Data Commons can allow data access via Open Cloud Mesh (OCM) and Web Distributed Authoring and Versioning (WebDAV), for example. The list of file access providers supported by **rclone** can give an overview over the great diversity of potential data access providers and protocols. Furthermore, we intend to allow use cases to implement data access logic specific to their deployment, such as fast local data access through CIFS, or local file system access.

As far as non-public datasets are concerned, proper authorization credentials must be passed through the Dispatcher to the execution environment. The credentials **will not** be included in the Request Package's RO-Crate, to make the Package reusable between users and safe for publishing. Rather than that, the credentials will be transferred along with the flow of requests between components using standard authorization headers, such as "X-Auth-Token" or "Authorization: Bearer", originating from the user session materialized in the EOSC Data Commons Portal or using an automated **OpenID Connect** flow in case of scripts and middleware software. This way, finally, the credentials will be passed to an execution environment, which will use them to authorize data access requests. To that end, further

implementation efforts are foreseen, correlated with building a mesh of compatibility between data sources and environments.

So far only *inputs* to the workflows were addressed. Regarding *outputs* of the workflows, further architecture discussion is needed. In the interactive case, the user is provided with access to the environment, and the responsibility for handling the outputs can be left to him/her. On the contrary, the batch mode will need more architecture discussion. For example, the RO-Crate could include a link to a pre-created draft record in a repository, but the exact specifications on how to gather the workflow output to be included in that record still need clarification.

2.5. On demand execution environments

Besides sending the workload to existing services (e.g. usegalaxy.eu, notebooks.egi.eu) the Dispatcher supports spawning dedicated short-lived services. In the PoC release, Infrastructure Manager is supported and deployment in Kubernetes is in development.

2.5.1. Infrastructure Manager

The Infrastructure Manager features an option to set up a VRE at runtime using a TOSCA template to specify the service's deployment requirements. In the case of RO-Crate files where the VRE instance is already deployed, only the destination url is specified:

```
JSON
{
  "@id": "#destination",
  "@type": "Service",
  "url": "https://usegalaxy.eu/"
}
```

Figure 6 – RO-Crate specification of an existing target VRE

The current available instances may not fit the amount of resources required for the user's experiment. The RO-Crate can be modified to specify a destination using a TOSCA template to define the deployment requirements of the service:

```
JSON
{
  "@id": "#destination",
  "@type": "Service",
  "serviceType": "InfrastructureManager",
  "name": "Galaxy",
  "memoryRequirements": "4 GiB",
  "processorRequirements": [
    "2 vCPU",
  ]
}
```

```

        "1 GPU"
    ],
    "storageRequirements": "200 GiB",
    "hasPart": [
        { "@id": "#galaxy.yaml" }
    ]
},
{
    "@id": "#galaxy.yaml",
    "@type": "File",
    "name": "Galaxy TOSCA template file",
    "encodingFormat": "text/yaml",
    "url": "https://raw.githubusercontent.com/.../templates/galaxy.yaml"
}

```

Figure 7 – ROCreate specification to spawn a dedicated instance of the target VRE

Finally, Infrastructure Manager returns the URL of the just-deployed VRE, and then this new instance is used in the same way as any other publicly available instance. The URL of the TOSCA template, which describes the cloud topology and hardware requirements, is defined in the RO-Crate file. The user may specify the field *memoryRequirements* to set the amount of RAM required. *processorRequirements* is an array where the number of CPUs and GPUs can be specified. Finally, *storageRequirements* enables the specification of the amount of hard disk space needed. All these values are finally set in the final TOSCA template that will be submitted to the Infrastructure Manager that will perform the final deployment. The requirements for storage and computing resources should ideally be extrapolated from properties of the data files and the tool or workflow that have been included in the Package.

Regarding authentication, the IM receives the user's OIDC access token from the Dispatcher to act on the user's behalf. Furthermore, the IM module of the Dispatcher enables the configuration of the cloud backends that will be used to perform the deployments. For OpenStack sites that are also connected to EGI Check-in, the same OIDC access token will be used to deploy cloud resources in the user space.

2.5.2. Kubernetes and interLink

Besides using existing VREs and creating on-demand environments via Infrastructure Manager (which targets cloud IaaS platforms in turn), use of **Kubernetes** to spawn environments which support full containerization is in development (using Scipion as pilot use case) as well.

In particular, **interLink** is an open-source software product capable of extending the container orchestration de-facto standard (Kubernetes) to support offloading to any type of resource provider (Cloud/HTC/HPC) transparently. This provides an API specification for integration of resources provisioned through different technologies and architectures, possibly geographically distributed, requiring little to no adaptation from the end user perspective.

The strategy is to enable a Kubernetes cluster to send containers/pods to a “virtual” node. This node seamlessly manages the entire lifecycle of containerized workloads, whether on a remote server or, preferably, within an HPC batch queue.

Transparency is granted by the fact that it keeps exposing the very same experience of running a pod on cloud resources, thanks to the native integration with the Kubernetes node management APIs.

The interLink project is composed by 3 main elements:

- **Virtual Kubelet:** responsible for communicating with the interLink API in order to manage Pod operation, such as adding, removing, querying pods to/from the cluster. For every registered Pod the Virtual Kubelet sends a Create HTTP call to the interLink API; a Status HTTP call to the interLink API is automatically issued to check every Pod's health. Finally if a job executed (by a Pod) is terminated, Pods are removed. HTTP is implemented following the REST standard. The body of every call is the same: a marshalled (JSON type) list of Pod descriptors, which are stored in variables of type v1.Pod, a built-in go-client standard Kubernetes type.
- **interLink API:** is the core of the service. It is responsible for translating Virtual Kubelet's HTTP calls into standard, agnostic outputs for the plugin-based structure.
- **Backend specific plugin:** The architecture is plugin-based and foresees a plugin for each distinct backend to be supported. So far **SLURM**, **docker**, **HTCondor** and **Unicore** are the major ones. For each API (VERB) the plugin performs specific operations based on what the actual backend is. Submitting a Pod to the cluster means the plugins will receive from interLink the list of all related Secrets, ConfigMaps, EmptyDirs and the description of the Pod itself. With these information the plugin takes specific actions accordingly

The current plan within EOSC Data Commons is to integrate interLink and the Dispatcher with two objectives. On the one side we plan to integrate interLink with JupyterHub enabling the transparent offloading of JupyterLabs over HPC sites. On the other side, once standard Kubernetes is made available at Dispatcher level, we will enable it with interLink. The latter approach will be exploited in order to study a generic implementation which might be technically suitable for any container-based workflow that is Kubernetes compliant. At the time of writing, an analysis of the RO-Crate extension is ongoing.

2.6. Implementation details

In the current design the Dispatcher is expected to be a fairly lightweight service, not capable of serving thousands of requests per second, and not running any significant processing with each request. As a result, it is installed on a single (virtual) machine, using Docker Compose to isolate individual components.

2.6.1. Ansible

Ansible is used to deploy the service in a reproducible way. Besides the production playbook, a development version intended for quick turnaround is provided. Sensitive information (OIDC

client secret in particular) is stored in encrypted Ansible vaults. Configuration files are templated with Ansible, allowing all deployment-specific information to be stored in one place.

2.6.2. Server certificate

The Dispatcher exposes HTTPS endpoint which requires a properly signed X509 certificate. It is acquired using [the Let's Encrypt service](#). Following [the best practices](#), the initial Docker Compose is used to start a simple nginx web server, to generate the certificate and to move it to a location where an unprivileged nginx Docker container is able to find it. The unprivileged nginx container is part of the main Docker Compose instead of standard nginx container for security reasons.

2.6.3. Main components

Figure 8 shows the main Dispatcher components and their interactions.

Figure 8 – Dispatcher components and their interactions

Entrypoint proxy

The entry point, the HTTPS network port, is handled by Nginx which provides the SSL layer, it routes requests according to prefix rules, and it manages access control HTTP headers.

Core service

Processing in the Core Service is generic: RO-Crate packages are parsed on input, and based on the workflow type, appropriate VRE-specific classes are called. The core is implemented in FastAPI, using Celery for the task queue. The authentication via EGI Check-in is implemented using the fastapi_oauth2 and social_core libraries.

VRE Plugins

The VRE plugins (located in the `/app/vres` directory) contain all available VRE implementations. VREs are implementations of the abstract class `VRE` and are instantiated by `VREFactory`. The abstract class also features an option to set up a dedicated service instance via Infrastructure Manager. For example, a Galaxy instance can be defined by a URL or a TOSCA template, which is executed and results in a virtual machine with Galaxy deployed on top of it. This is then used in the same way as a public Galaxy instance.

Support services

Binder integration requires exposing the workflow (Jupyter notebook) and miscellaneous input data as a temporary git repository, which is served by FastCGI wrapper.

SSL certificates (initially requested from Let's Encrypt in the bootstrap stage) are renewed periodically by Certbot.

2.6.4. Error handling

The custom exceptions are defined in `app.exceptions` and they cover a variety of domain errors – the VRE parser in `app.routers.utils.vre` raises `VREConfigurationError` with the specific configuration issue. This exception is caught in the parse function and then the `HTTPException` from `fastapi.exceptions` is raised, which propagates to the user. Platform-specific exception classes, for example `GalaxyAPIError`, are defined.

Because many exceptions are a consequence of the API timing out or being temporarily down/under maintenance, the native Celery retry mechanism using exponential backoff is used. If all retries are unsuccessful the task ends with status: `FAILURE`.

2.6.5. CI/CD

We use GitHub CI/CD pipelines to deploy the service. Currently, there are 2 pipelines in place:

1. "Build, lint and test" builds the project, runs **Black formatter**, lint checks, and then unit tests. This pipeline is executed on pushes and pull requests to the master branch.
2. "Deploy to stable" uses Ansible to deploy the newest version to the *stable dev instance of Dispatcher*. Runs on pushes to the master branch. This is safe, as the first pipeline prevents merging if it fails and a review of a pull request is required. A healthcheck is also included in this pipeline to notify about unexpected deployment errors (for example in case of some dependency issues).

3. Interaction with VREs

3.1. Galaxy

The input RO-Crate package for **Galaxy** contains a reference to the Galaxy workflow file as a mandatory item, and references to input files eventually.

The integration with the Dispatcher is implemented via *Galaxy workflow_landings* API call. The Dispatcher translates the references from the input to this API and makes a POST request to create a *workflow claim*, which is returned to the user in turn. The user follows the link, ending at the Galaxy page with the workflow prepared to run on the specified inputs.

The POST request does not trigger any processing at Galaxy side, and it can be called unauthenticated. On the contrary, the user must authenticate when accessing the claim URL.

3.2. Jupyter and Binder

The Dispatcher supports executing Jupyter notebooks via the **Binder interface** in its current release. The input RO-Crate contains references to a Jupyter notebook and additional input files (alternatively, those can be also embedded). The Dispatcher transforms the RO-Crate to a temporary git repository, which is used, together with the specified Binder destination, to construct the redirect URL returned to the user. Once the user follows it (authenticating with the Binder destination if required), Binder clones the temporary repository, hence retrieving the notebook and the inputs, and prepares the whole environment for the user.

We also considered direct access to JupyterHub for use cases that cannot be transformed to the outlined Binder approach. However, the access to JupyterHub must be authenticated, and because its implementation is focused on direct browser access (i.e. not a service acting on user's behalf), handling the authentication workflow driven by the Dispatcher is not straightforward, and further design discussions will be required.

3.3. Modama

The web GUI to browse data in **Modama** currently implements a simple workflow similar to the Dispatcher. For a given file in Modama, it can calculate URLs for the following targets:

- Browse folder in our local **Nextcloud** instance,
- Browse folder in our local JupyterHub instance,
- Preview file or folder with **LiberTEM**,
- Preview file in an image viewer,
- Search for references in local instances of electronic lab notebooks.

These URLs are presented to the user in the Graphical User Interface (GUI) and take them to these services. At the same time, the URL for viewing a particular file or folder in the browsing web GUI can serve as a universal link target to refer to a specific file or folder in the repository. We made sure these URLs have a canonical encoding with a 1:1 mapping between file name

and generated URL even in the presence of special characters. Currently, the choice of tools as well as URL construction functions for each target are hard-coded in the web GUI. It relies on a known mount point of the file repository on the target services.

We use the JupyterHub instance and [Jupyter Server Proxy](#) for authentication, SSL and as a launcher for LiberTEM and the image viewer. That way we ensure that the back-end processes for these services run under the Unix identity of the logged-in user.

For other web services such as the management interface itself and the Nextcloud integration, we access the data through a WebDAV server that was modified in such a way that a WebDAV server worker process assumes the identity of the user for which the request is made while accessing data.

With both methods we ensure that all file system access is performed with the Unix user identity, and thus file system limitations are enforced.

The interaction between the services doesn't require specific shared code and only relies on services that interpret GET URLs in a predictable way. As a result, individual services are easy to upgrade, failures remain local to a specific service or integration, many integrations can be added without requiring collaboration on the target side, and the integration is not specific to one pair of services, but open to alternative link sources.

Current drawbacks are a very limited choice of integrations that are hard-coded in our GUI, as well as being limited to files in our repository. By participating in EOSC Data Commons we hope to improve the configurability of integrations. At the same time, we are happy about the simplicity, robustness, and broad interoperability of our solution, and hope to carry this over to EOSC Data Commons. In particular, this means keeping the interface between search GUI and dispatchers slim and open, ideally with a simple GET URL that is also open to other link sources, such as alternative search engines or other tools.

Furthermore, we hope to allow our users processing of external data from participating repositories on our infrastructure.

3.4. ScienceMesh

CERN runs the [CERNBox](#) service, an Enterprise File Sync&Share (EFSS) system integrated with the Laboratory's computing infrastructure and its several applications and workflows. It is open source and maintained by CERN and others. [ScienceMesh](#) is a federation of such systems. It allows users of each system to share data and applications with users of the others, without any shared Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI).

At the end of the project we want to be able to support HPC processing on ScienceMesh via CephFS integration to CERNBox, making data directly available to processing resources (JupyterLab and HPC).

ScienceMesh is planning to integrate with the EOSC Data Commons Service in the following ways:

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- Integrated with discovery mechanisms.
- Ingestion and processing of search results.
- Publishing data to digital repositories.

The EOSC EU Node and the EOSC Federation are providing the same storage federation technology, based on [Open Cloud Mesh \(OCM\)](#). OCM v1.2 support is implemented in CERNBox, and its Jupyter integration is extended to fulfill the Data Commons workflows.

Integration of ScienceMesh into the EOSC Data player will happen by the development of a ScienceMeshVRE class in the *Dispatcher* that will dispatch packages for processing to a ScienceMesh node through OCM shares embedding an RO-Crate.

The ScienceMesh node (in this case CERNBox) will then process this package by downloading the data required for the analysis from the respective repositories and perform the analysis.

Authorization in the OCM protocol requires trust between the sender and the receiver: in this case the Dispatcher acts as a sender, and exposes a */.well-known/ocm* endpoint featuring a JSON payload similar to the one below:

```
JSON
{
  "enabled": true,
  "apiVersion": "1.2.0",
  "endpoint": "dispatcher.egi.eu"
  "resourceTypes": [
    {
      "name": "ro-crate":
      "shareTypes": [
        "user"
      ],
      "protocols": {
        "embedded": ""
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 8 – Example of content returned by the */.well-known/ocm* endpoint

This payload signals the ability of the Dispatcher to offer RO-Crates *embedded* in an OCM payload.

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The actual dispatch request is sent as a POST request to the ScienceMesh instance's OCM endpoint, containing the embedded RO-Crate and an OCM address to identify the receiver (e.g. *some.user@cernbox.cern.ch*). The ScienceMesh node receives this request and verifies the server that sent the package using the */.well-known/ocm* endpoint described above. A key point here is that this is the only required verification, as the OCM protocol and its endpoints are unauthenticated by design, and trust can be augmented via HTTP signatures (however this is not yet implemented). The OCM share is stored in the ScienceMesh node with the embedded RO-Crate ready for processing. The flow from the dispatcher to the ScienceMesh instance is detailed in [Figure 9](#).

Figure 9 – User interaction with EOSC Data Commons services targeting Science Mesh

The current status of the integration is that a package can be sent via an OCM share from the Dispatcher using the ScienceMeshVRE class. The package is then received and stored in CERNBox. The processing of the package (e.g. download of data and analysis) still requires further implementation, it can be displayed in a naive way in the CERNBox interface but further frontend work is required to enable the processing of the package.

A CephFS driver has been developed and is currently being tested to enable processing on local HPC resources; this implementation is required to enable the full workflow. The CERNBox OCM implementation has been brought up to speed, and the EOSC OCM Federation was demonstrated at the EOSC Symposium on the 3rd of November 2025.

Our integration plan for full workflow support is the following:

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- Developing an extension for the CERNBox web interface and displaying the RO-Crate in a way that is user-friendly.
- The processing of the package itself, e.g. downloading data and analysis from the repositories and storing these in CERNBox.
- The CephFS driver and Jupyter integration to enable processing and storage on HPC computing infrastructure
- Adaptations in the Dispatcher and Matchmaker to account for changes.

Additional goals include:

- Sync functionality on both desktop and mobile clients.
- Support for authenticated and public shares on HPC data.
- Demo of processing data on HPC via command-line operations.

3.5. FAIR Molecular Dynamics

Integration with the [Molecular Dynamic Dashboard \(MDDash\)](#) is in progress. MDDash uses customized JupyterHub internally to manage isolated users' environments in Kubernetes. Integration with the Dispatcher requires creating the specific user environment first by talking to this JupyterHub API. Once it is ready, input files can be transferred by calling the MDDash API.

The critical part of this integration is authentication – the Dispatcher must act on the user's behalf, which will require modifications on the MDDash side to handle delegated tokens instead of leveraging the usual OIDC login handshake.

3.6. Haddock

[Haddock](#) provides a complex web interface for multiple biomolecule analysis tasks. Besides being available as a web service operated by the development team, it can be also deployed privately.

The currently developed Dispatcher integration uses existing Infrastructure Manager recipes to create a virtual cluster with all required Haddock services. Once the cluster is ready, input files referenced in the RO-Crate will be uploaded to the newly created Haddock cluster, and a link to its web interface will be passed to the user.

4. Proof-of-concept integration

In the first eight months of the project the partners worked on initial specifications and architectural design and implementation of prototypes. All those efforts have been put together in order to prepare a PoC integration, serving as an important milestone and validation of the design decisions made so far.

The PoC was built around an end-to-end scenario that requires interaction of most of the EOSC Data Commons components with each other. It uses **Onedata** as the data source, which integrates data and metadata from one of the project's repositories (**DaSCH**), and **Galaxy** as the execution environment. The whole flow through the system components and external services is depicted in **Figure 10**.

Detailed breakdown of the consecutive steps:

1. **The PoC dataset** is imported into Onedata by reference – no data is copied in the process, but a lightweight file metadata entry is created. At the same time, descriptive dataset metadata in the DataCite format is collected and attached to the virtualized dataset. In the process, a suitable crawler may be developed by the Onedata team working together by the repository owners to collect the data references and metadata, and register the datasets in Onedata to be made available to EOSC Data Commons. The following scenarios are supported:
 - Collecting data references:
 - The repository exposes the data via a protocol that is supported by Onedata and allows remote access (HTTP, XRootD, WebDAV, NFS, S3). In this case, protocol-specific reference is stored for later access. The crawler traverses all datasets and files (if possible), or a different approach is used; for instance, ingesting a complete dump of the Repository database. Authenticated access is supported; Onedata allows specifying credentials for those remote storage types.
 - The repository stores its data on a local storage supported by Onedata (POSIX/block, Ceph, S3, NFS, Swift, GlusterFS, WebDAV, XRootD) and is willing to host a Oneprovider component. The mechanism for data ingestion is used; Oneprovider scans the data located on the storage system and registers corresponding file metadata entries, without data copying. Storage-specific access credentials are supported.
 - The repository uses proprietary solutions for data storage and does not offer an external API for data access. In this case, it is possible to ingest the data into Onedata by copying the whole content, though it is a last-resort solution.
 - Collecting metadata references:
 - The repository exposes an Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) endpoint:
 - The repository supports the DataCite format. Onedata can then aggregate the dataset metadata and expose it through its OAI-PMH interface, effectively proxying the information without modifications.

- The repository supports other metadata formats. The records are harvested by Onedata and a repository-specific procedure to map the metadata to DataCite is applied. The original record metadata is kept in the provenance ("about") section of the DataCite record, to the extent possible.
- The repository does not expose an OAI-PMH endpoint. The crawler must be able to resolve a comprehensive list of datasets offered by the repository, using arbitrary mechanisms within the crawler implementation. Metadata entries can be built in two ways:
 - The repository implements some proprietary metadata annotation mechanisms. The metadata is mapped to DataCite, and in this way, public data records in Onedata are built. The original metadata is retained, to the extent possible, using the additional information section in the corresponding DataCite record.
 - The repository does not store any metadata related to the datasets. In this case, either the most basic metadata can be generated based on file metadata, or the repository owners may use the Onedata APIs or UI to annotate the collected datasets, so that they become meaningful for the EOSC Data Commons Metadata Warehouse.

This approach has a strong integrative benefit for repositories that do not offer an OAI-PMH endpoint or metadata in the right format. By onboarding the data to Onedata, whose compliance with other components is ensured within the project, those data sources may offer their data to the users without developing new functionalities.

2. Datasets from all integrated repositories, including Onedata, along with their descriptive metadata (DataCite), are harvested through OAI-PMH by the Metadata Warehouse component. The harvesting is regular and incremental; the Warehouse incorporates all changes in repositories that have taken place since the last harvesting to update its aggregated view of the collections. In the process, suitable indices are built using the gathered metadata to allow later querying.
3. The user enters the EOSC Data Commons (EDC) Portal (Web UI), logs in, and searches for datasets.
4. The UI application makes a query to the Metadata Warehouse, according to the keywords and search options provided by the user.
5. The UI displays matching datasets, ordered by accuracy rating, to the user. The user chooses a **dataset** and a tool (**workflow**) for analysis. In the target scenario, compatible tools would be found in tool repositories by the Matchmaker in a similar way as the dataset. In this PoC scenario, an image of an old newspaper is processed using a fixed workflow with OCR tools and text analysis tools to produce a word cloud representing the most common words.
6. The UI queries the FileMetrix service to find out specific files contained in the dataset and their basic file metadata (names, sizes, mimetypes). It displays the results to the user.
7. The user chooses in the UI what files should be used for execution and how they should be mapped to the analysis inputs. In the case of this PoC flow, the Galaxy workflow inputs.

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Figure 10 – Overall interactions among the user and all involved components in the PoC demonstration

8. When the user is satisfied with his/her choices and ready, he/she starts the analysis.
9. The UI creates the Request Package based on user choices. Currently, the Request Packager component is implemented in the form of a prototype within the UI application. The target solution assumes it's a separate component with an API. The Request Package produced for this scenario can be found in [the Dispatcher GitHub repository](#).
10. The UI calls the Dispatcher API with the Request Package to run the analysis.

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11. The Dispatcher identifies the execution environment and translates the Request Package into platform-specific information and API calls. In the case of Galaxy, it uses the “Workflow Landing” API to prepare a workflow with predefined inputs, ready to be executed.
12. The UI displays the landing page URL to the user, so that the user can follow it and be prompted to log in to the Galaxy interface and run the execution.
13. While the workflow is running, it reads the remote input data from Onedata, which in turn reads the remote dataset from the DaSCH service and serves it. In the future, an improvement is foreseen to allow direct data read (13c in Fig. 5) from the original source using methods such as HTTP redirects on Onedata level.
14. The user may monitor the execution using the Galaxy UI or APIs, and when the execution is finished, access the results – the word cloud built based on the newspaper image processed with Optical character recognition (OCR).

This PoC entails an end-to-end flow through the system and has proven that the envisioned architecture and protocol/component specifications are suitable to achieve the project goals. While it shows integration with only two data sources and one execution environment, the generic approach and abstracted interfaces that have been developed in the process promise now a faster integration of further repositories and VREs.

Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
CPU	Central Processing Unit
EFSS	Enterprise File Sync&Share
GPU	Graphics processing unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Tech Computer Corporation
IM	Infrastructure manager
MDDash	Molecular Dynamic Dashboard
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OCM	Open Cloud Mesh
OCR	Optical character recognition
OIDC	OpenID Connect
PoC	Proof of concept
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
uuid	Unique identifier
UI	User Interface
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WebDAV	Web Distributed Authoring and Versioning